

SolACE

Solutions for improving Agroecosystem and
Crop Efficiency for water and nutrient use

Stakeholders' Event

Foggia, Italy

16th May 2018

SolACE is a European Horizon 2020 project aiming at improving water and nutrient use efficiency of crops and agroecosystems. It focuses on 3 economically important crops; bread wheat, durum wheat, and potato. The goal? To achieve lower input-dependency in conventional systems, while achieving higher efficiency within organic systems, combined with the low-input principle (ecological intensification).

The event will take place in the framework of the Durum Days in Foggia, Italy (www.durumdays.com).

SolACE Innovations – Your experience and feedback are necessary!

SolACE is a multi-actor project and engages with a broad range of stakeholders, e.g. farmers, farm advisors, breeders, agribusiness actors, etc. to promote strong interactions across the whole production chain.

We want to show you some of the innovations that the project is working on and receive your critical and valuable feedback and comments. Doing so, we may produce solutions that are useful in practise and will make a difference at a large-scale.

This is a free event, presented in both English and Italian and includes refreshments.

Venue

Chamber of Commerce and Industry of Foggia (CCIF)

Viale Fortore 141, 71121 Foggia FG, Italy

Programme

14:00 – 14:30	Registration at the Chamber of Commerce of Foggia
14:30 – 14:45	Quick introduction to concept of event
14:45 – 16:30	Crop and soil management innovation presentations > Second generation microbial inoculants (Bread wheat & potato) > Genotypes mixtures (Durum wheat) > Decision Support Systems (Bread & Durum wheat)
16:30 – 17:00	Coffee and refreshments
17:00 – 18:30	Breeding & phenotyping innovation presentations > Bread wheat hybrids for improved tolerance against water & nitrogen > Participatory breeding schemes (Durum wheat). > Accounting for below-ground traits for improving tolerance against water / nitrogen deficiency (Bread wheat).

Registration

www.solace-eu.net

Contact

Dr. Philippe Hinsinger, INRA UMR Eco&Sols , Montpellier, France

philippe.hinsinger@inra.fr

Dr. Nichola Pecchini, CREA, Foggia, Italy

nicola.pecchioni@crea.gov.it

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 727247 (SolACE)

Schweizerische Eidgenossenschaft
Confédération suisse
Confederazione Svizzera
Confederaziun svizra

Swiss Confederation

Federal Department of Economic Affairs,
Education and Research EAER
State Secretariat for Education,
Research and Innovation SERI